

Zoochemical Profiling of *Meretrix casta* (Mollusca: Bivalvia) Extracts and Their Antibacterial Property

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Abstract

Meretrix casta has long been recognised for its nutritional value and traditional medicinal applications. This research explores the bioactive compounds present in methanol, ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts of *M. casta*, and evaluate their antibacterial and antibiofilm efficacy against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a clinically significant, biofilm-forming pathogen. The bioactive compounds in the extracts were examined using UV-Vis spectroscopy, FTIR, and GC-MS techniques, and the findings revealed the occurrence of diverse bioactive compounds like fatty acids, phenolics, and cholesterol derivatives. Antibacterial activities were assessed via agar well diffusion method, MIC, and Resazurin-based cell viability assay. Out of the three extracts, methanolic extract recorded the maximum activity (MIC = 6.25 µg/mL; IC₅₀ = 1.59 µg/mL), followed by ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts. Interestingly, the methanolic extract also exhibited biofilm inhibition, disrupting >50% at 25 µg/mL. These results indicate that *M. casta* extracts have potential as a resource of antibacterial and antibiofilm agents effective against *P. aeruginosa*.

Keywords— Marine Bioactive Compounds, Traditional Medicine, Biofilm Disruption, Bioactive Compounds, Antibiofilm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spanning over 70% of the Earth's surface, the ocean harbours an extraordinary diversity of life forms, with marine ecosystems accounting nearly 95% of the biosphere[1]. This ecosystem is inhabited by organisms that produce a wide array of structurally diverse natural products, known as secondary metabolites, which primarily function as defence mechanisms. These compounds have evolved as an adaptation to the extreme environmental conditions like salinity, pressure and availability of light [2,3]. Marine invertebrates, in particular, are increasingly recognised for their biomedical potential due to the presence of terpenoids, steroids, alkaloids, ethers, phenols, and peptides more abundantly than marine plants or microbes [4]. Among the group of invertebrates, molluscs occupy a wide range of habitats, from freshwater streams and lakes to the deep sea, exhibiting a spectrum of ecological and evolutionary adaptations [5]. Clams inhabiting intertidal zones, for instance, have evolved complex biochemical mechanisms to withstand alternating periods of submersion and exposure [6].

Molluscs have long been an essential component of human nutrition and indigenous medicine, especially in coastal areas. Among them, *Meretrix casta*, a marine bivalve mollusc, secures a notable status due to its nutritional profile and medicinal potential [7]. *M. casta* is highly valued for its high-quality protein, essential omega 3 fatty acids, and micronutrients such as iron, magnesium, zinc etc. [8]. Additionally, the traditional use of *M. casta* in folk medicines suggests the occurrence of bioactive compounds with promising pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial effects. However, there is no scientific evidence to claim this. Hence, the present study aims to profile the zoochemical (bioactive compounds) present in extracts and to evaluate antibacterial and antibiofilm properties of ethyl acetate, methanolic and aqueous extracts against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a clinically significant opportunistic pathogen known for its biofilm-forming capability. *M. casta*, being a rich reservoir of bioactive compounds, holds potential for developing novel and effective treatments for bacterial infections.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Marine invertebrates, especially molluscs, are emerging as potential sources of Zoochemicals and bioactive compounds with great therapeutic potential [9]. Marine invertebrates including phyla such as Porifera, Molluscs, and Echinoderms yield a variety of secondary metabolites. In the Philippines, sea star species (*Linckia laevigata*, *Protoreaster nodosus*, *Acanthaster planci*) were found to be rich in alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, triterpenoids, and cardiac glycosides, mainly saponins and steroids, with promising potential for drug discovery [10]. Freshwater clam (*Corbicula fluminea*) extracts were found to contain secondary metabolites like terpenoids, phenols, tannins, saponins, steroids, and alkaloids, with ethanol giving the highest yield and antioxidant benefits. Ethanol also showed the best extraction efficiency in molluscan shells, further validating the medicinal potential of marine Mollusca [11]. *Meretrix casta* extracts exhibited antioxidant, α -amylase inhibition, and glucose uptake activity, highlighting potential in diabetes and oxidative stress therapies [5]. Around 96 marine-derived compounds have shown strong antibacterial and antifungal properties, including against the resistant strains, supporting their application in novel antibiotic strategies [12]. Molluscs produce diverse secondary metabolites such as peptides, sterols, terpenes, prostaglandins, and alkaloids with unique bioactivities, and species like *C. amadis*, *C. betulinus*, *L. lambis*, *T. dolium*, *T. radiatus*, and *H. cochlidium* were found to show effective antibacterial activity [13].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Specimen Collection and Identification

Meretrix casta, also known as the yellow clam, was gathered from an offshore location nearly 300 m from the coastal bank of Rameswaram (located at 9.2876° North latitude and 79.3129° East longitude), Tamil Nadu, India. Live *M. casta* specimens were hand-collected and identified based on morphological features using a field identification key and confirmed via the World Registry of Marine Species (WoRMS). Following specimen recognition, the clams were stored in suitable solvents and brought to the laboratory for further analysis. In the lab, the shells were gently opened using a sharp sterile blade to preserve the soft tissue. The flesh was then carefully rinsed several times with running water to eliminate any surface debris or impurities, and a final wash with distilled water was given to ensure purity for downstream applications.

B. Preparation of Crude Extract

The soft tissues of *M. casta* were dried under shade, powdered and underwent Soxhlet extraction with three solvents: aqueous (AQ), ethyl acetate (EA) and methanol (MT). Approximately 50 g of the powdered sample was packed into a thimble and extracted with 250 mL of the respective solvent separately for 6–8 hours. Following extraction, the obtained extracts were clarified using Whatman No.1 filter paper and then concentrated under reduced pressure by means of a rotary evaporator [14]. The obtained concentrated crude extracts were further dried under vacuum and preserved in sterile containers at 4°C for further use.

C. Characterization of *M. casta* Extracts

Spectral analysis of MT, EA and AQ extracts was performed (at 200-800nm) to determine the presence of various Zoochemicals such as flavonoids, phenolics, pigments, etc., using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan; Model: UV-1800) with a slit width of 2nm, using a 10-mm quartz cuvette at room temperature. For each extract, the corresponding solvent was used as the blank [15,16]. The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy over the spectral range of 4000 to 400cm⁻¹ was done to analyse the functional groups such as -OH-COOH, -NH₂ and C=O in all the three extracts. These functional groups indicate the occurrence of secondary metabolites like saponins, alkaloids, tannins proteins [17]. Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was carried out to detect the active molecules and elucidate the chemical composition of the *M. casta* extracts. Volatile components of the extract were

analysed by GC–MS (Agilent 7890A GC system coupled to a 5975C MS detector). The compounds were identified on the basis of retention time and spectral comparison with NIST library data. This technique is well-suited to detect small to medium molecular weight bioactive compounds like esters, fatty acids, terpenes and hydrocarbons.

D. Bacterial Isolation and Identification

The bacterial samples were taken from moist areas near the kitchen sink with the help of sterile cotton swabs by rubbing the sample surface in a twirling motion. The swab head was then broken and put into 2mL sterile water, which was subsequently used to inoculate Luria-Bertani (LB) agar plates [18]. The isolated bacterial colony was quadrant streaked and subjected to molecular identification [19].

E. Antibacterial Activity Assay

Antibacterial activity of all three extracts, EA, MT and AQ, of *M. casta* was assessed using the agar well diffusion assay [20]. An aliquot of 100µl of overnight culture of the isolated bacteria was evenly spread onto solidified LB Agar plates. Wells of a diameter of 9mm were bored in the agar plate using a sterile cork borer, and 100 and 200µg/ml were introduced into the wells in their respective plates. The three extracts were diluted using sterilized distilled water to make the desired concentrations. Streptomycin was used as the positive control, and sterilized distilled water served as the negative control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, after which the antibacterial potential of the three extracts was assessed by recording the zone of inhibition around the wells, which are clear regions devoid of bacterial growth. The zone of inhibition diameter(mm) was recorded.

F. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The MIC of each extract was assessed using the 96-well microplate assay [21]. To all the wells, 100µl of the overnight culture of the isolated bacteria was added. Ten serial dilutions of each extract, 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.125, 1.56, 0.78, 0.39 and 0.19 µg/mL were prepared. A 100µL volume of overnight bacterial culture, followed by 100 µL of each dilution, was loaded to each well and incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. Streptomycin (100 µg/mL) and sterilized distilled water were used as the positive and negative controls, respectively. The plates were sealed and kept for incubation for 24 hours at 37°C[22]. The bacterial growth was measured by recording the turbidity at 595nm in a microtiter plate reader, and IC₅₀ graphs were plotted [23]. The percentage inhibition of bacterial growth by the extracts was calculated using the equation given below:

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \times 100$$

Where A₀= Absorbance of control and A₁= Absorbance of the sample.

G. Resazurin Cell Viability Assay

Resazurin cell viability assay was carried out directly in the MIC plates to assess bacterial cell viability and metabolic activity under different concentrations of the extracts. A 1mg/mL stock concentration of resazurin was diluted 1:30 with sterilised distilled water and stored at the dark [24]. From this, a 75µL working solution was loaded into each well and incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes in dark. The colour change was then assessed by direct visual examination. Cell viability was indicated by colour change from purple to pink (or colourless) [25].

H. Anti-Biofilm Assay

The potential of ET, MT and AQ extracts of *M. casta* against the disruption of biofilm was assessed in a microtiter plate [26]. Overnight bacterial culture (100 μ l) was added to 100 μ l of LB broth in the wells of a 96-well flat-bottom plate and then incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs without shaking to facilitate proper attachment of bacteria to the biofilm as well as to develop multilayer biofilm. Following the incubation period, the media were removed from the 96-well microtiter plates and varying concentrations of the three extracts were added, followed by incubation at 37°C for another 24 hours. Streptomycin served as the positive control, while sterilized distilled water and LB broth served as negative control. Quantification of the biofilm disruption was measured using crystal violet (CV) staining assay [27]. Following the next incubation, the plates were washed with sterilized distilled water three times to eliminate the loosely attached bacteria and planktonic cells. The plates were then air dried for 40 minutes, and 200 μ l of 1% crystal violet solution was applied to stain the biofilm in each well for 15 minutes. After staining, the wells were rinsed three times with sterilized distilled water. Biofilms were observed as purple rings around the sides of the wells. To quantify the remaining biofilm, 200 μ L of 90% ethanol was added for solubilizing the retained stain in the wells. From this, 100 μ L was transferred into another microtiter plate to measure the OD at 595nm using microtiter plate reader [28].

The percentage inhibition of biofilm by the extracts was determined using the equation below [22]:

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \times 100$$

Where A_0 = Absorbance of control and A_1 = Absorbance of the sample.

I. Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and the data were expressed as mean \pm SD (standard deviation). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Duncan's multiple range test, was performed to evaluate the statistically significant differences using IBM SPSS Statistics software, version 21. $p \leq 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant [20].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Zoochemical Characterization of *M. casta* Extracts

UV–Visible spectral analysis of *Meretrix casta* extracts was performed to evaluate the presence of conjugated systems, aromatic rings, chromophores and compounds containing σ -bonds, π bonds and lone pair of electrons. Distinct absorbance peaks suggest the existence of bioactive compounds [15]. The data obtained by UV-VIS spectroscopic analysis of EA, AT and AQ extracts of *M. casta* are presented in Table I.

TABLE II
UV-VIS PEAK VALUES OF ETHYL ACETATE (EA), METHANOLIC (MT) AND AQUEOUS (AQ) EXTRACTS OF *M. CASTA*

Sl. No	Wavelength(nm)		
	EA	MT	AQ
1	666.00	665.00	371.50
2	606.00	608.50	357.00
3	533.00	535.00	340.00
4	504.00	504.00	323.50
5	407.00	392.50	302.50

6	373.00	364.00	283.50
7	358.50	354.50	239.50
8	348.00	345.00	
9	333.00	334.00	
10	319.00	324.50	
11	307.00	291.00	
12	294.00	279.50	
13	276.00	265.00	
14	254.50	252.50	
15	238.00	239.00	
16	227.00	228.50	
17		220.50	
18		211.00	
19		204.50	

All three extracts exhibited significant absorbance in the UV region, indicating the presence of conjugated compounds capable of absorbing UV light. Among them, MT extract showed broader and more intense absorbance ranging from UV to visible region, suggesting a higher concentration or greater diversity of UV and visible light absorbing compounds. A distinct peak at 665nm suggests the presence of porphyrin or heme-related compounds (Fig. 1a). EA extract displayed a visible peak at 666nm, indicating the presence of aromatic or pigmented compounds (Fig. 1b). In contrast, AQ extract showed no visible range peaks but demonstrated strong UV absorption, pointing to the occurrence of polar UV-active compounds like phenolics or small peptides (Fig. 1c). The consistent absorbance plateau ($A=4.000$) observed across the 200–400 nm range in all extracts suggests a high concentration of conjugated molecules, such as phenolics and flavonoids, characterised by strong electronic transitions. Thus, UV–Visible spectroscopy was used efficiently for the detection of chromophoric groups present in the bioactive molecules in the three extracts of *M. casta* [16]. Interestingly, porphyrins have also been identified in other marine snails like *Clanculus pharaonius* and *Clanculus margaritarius*, where they serve as shell colour pigments [29]. Additionally, in *Perna viridis*, commonly known as Indian green mussel, the presence of phenolics and flavonoids has been reported. These findings align with the UV-Vis spectral results obtained in the current study, reinforcing the presence of UV and Visible light-absorbing bioactive compounds in *M. casta*.

Fig. 1 UV-VIS peak values of 1a. Ethyl acetate, 1b. Methanolic, 1c. Aqueous extracts of *M. casta*

FTIR analysis was performed to identify functional groups within the EA, MT and AQ extracts of *M. casta*, based on the peak value in the infrared radiation region (Fig 2). The results revealed that the absorption bands in the region 3300 cm^{-1} across all extracts are due to O-H stretching vibrations, confirming the presence of hydroxyl groups [15]. The absorption band near 2927 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the symmetric C-H stretching vibrations of the saturated sp^3 hybridized carbon atoms. The absorption band around 1633 cm^{-1} corresponds to the bending vibration of retained water, which is common in biological extracts. However, the overlapping contributions from C=C stretching may also be present. Additionally, the bands between 1510 and 1610 cm^{-1} range are characteristic of C=C stretching vibrations in aromatic rings or conjugated alkenes present in the extract. The vibrational absorption bands around the range of 1450 - 1350 cm^{-1} can be attributed to C-H bending vibrations, typically due to methyl and methylene groups in the aliphatic molecules. Notable bands between 1240 and 1050 cm^{-1} are attributed to C-O stretching vibrations of alcohols, ethers or esters. Bands observed in the range of 985 - 822 cm^{-1} correspond to out-of-plane bending vibrations of =C-H bonds near to C=C bonds, typical of alkenes and substituted aromatic rings [15]. Finally, peaks in the low-frequency region in the range of 418 - 473 cm^{-1} indicate aromatic ring deformation vibrations, supporting the presence of aromatic systems in the extracts. Overall, the FTIR analysis of the three extracts of *M. casta* detected the presence of diverse functional groups, including hydroxyl, aromatic, aliphatic and conjugated systems (Table II-IV). The characteristic absorption bands confirmed the presence

of phenolic compounds, esters or ethers, saturated hydrocarbons and aromatic moieties, highlighting the structurally diverse nature of the bioactive compounds in the extracts. These findings are further supported by similar functional groups reported in a freshwater mollusc, *Pila globosa*, such as C-H, C=O, O-H and C=C [30]. Similarly, O-H stretching ($3000\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is observed in ethyl acetate-methanolic extracts of some commonly edible molluscs (*Amphioctopus marginatus*, *Crassostrea madrasensis*, *Uroteuthis duvaucelii*, and *Sepiella inermis*), which indicates the presence of hydroxyl-containing compounds like phenols and alcohols [31]. Additionally, the *M. casta* extracts showed similar FTIR profiles with a mollusc, *Babylonia spirata*, known for its significant antimicrobial activity, reinforcing the presence of comparable bioactive constituents in the studied extracts as well [32].

Fig. 2 FTIR spectrum of 2a. Ethyl acetate, 2b. Methanolic, 2c. Aqueous extracts of *M. casta*

TABLE II

FTIR SPECTRAL PEAK VALUES OF ETHYL ACETATE EXTRACT OF *M. CASTA*

Wave numbers (cm^{-1})	Assignments
3337.29	O-H stretching
2924.59	C-H stretching
2853.19	C-H stretching
1710.77	C=O stretching
1613.66	C=C stretching
1510.84	C=C stretching

1453.73	C-H bending
1242.38	C-O stretching
1026.75	C-O stretching
985.34	C=C bending
825.39	C=C bending
418.41	Aromatic rings

TABLE III

FTIR Spectral Peak Values of Methanolic Extract of *M. casta*

Wave numbers (cm^{-1})	Assignments
3308.73	O-H stretching
2927.45	C-H stretching
1605.09	C=C stretching
1510.85	C=C stretching
1356.62	C-H bending
1259.52	C-O stretching
1026.75	C-O stretching
919.65	C=C bending
822.54	C=C bending
472.68	Aromatic rings
418.41	Aromatic rings

TABLE IV

FTIR Spectral Peak Values of Aqueous Extract of *M. casta*

Wave numbers (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments
3324.44	O-H stretching
2927.45	C-H stretching
1607.95	C=C stretching
1517.98	C=C stretching
1446.58	C-H bending
1376.61	C-H bending
1273.79	C-O stretching
1165.27	C-O stretching
1038.17	C-O stretching
881.09	C=C bending
428.41	Aromatic rings

GC-MS analysis was employed to detect volatile and semi-volatile bioactive compounds in *M. casta* extracts. The chromatogram revealed multiple peaks with distinct retention times, indicating the presence of diverse bioactive compounds and are presented in (Fig 3) [33]. The chemical constituents of the *M. casta* extracts identified by the GC-MS analysis are listed along with their retention time and peak area % (Table V-VII). The GC-MS screening revealed the presence of 11, 13 and 11 compounds identified in the ethyl acetate, methanolic and aqueous extracts, respectively. The chromatogram of EA extract showed 11 prominent peaks which are dominated by Cholesterol (39.81%), Pentadecanoic acid (17.75%), Butanoic acid (8.72%), Butanoic acid, 3-methyl- (8.49%), Octadecanoic acid (7.14%), 9-Tetradecenal, (Z)- (5.06%), Propanoic acid, 2-methyl- (2.83%), Butanoic acid, 2-methyl- (2.78%), Pentadecanoic acid (2.46%), cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid (1.93%), Eicosanoic acid (1.83%), Cholest-5-en-3-ol (3. beta.)-, carbonochloridate (1.19%). Similarly, the chromatogram of MT extract revealed the presence of 13 prominent peaks which are dominated by n-Hexadecanoic acid (22.16%), Butanoic acid (12.65%), Butanoic acid, 3-methyl- (11.42%), Pentadecanoic acid (8.87%), 2-Piperidinone (7.86%), Thymine (6.31%), cis9-Hexadecenal (5.87%), Butanoic acid, 2-methyl- (3.86%), Propanoic acid, 2-methyl- (3.83%), Benzeneacetic acid (3.83%), Pentadecanoic acid (2.73%), Decane, 1,1diethoxy- (2.08%), 6-Pentadecenoic acid, 13-methyl-, (6Z)- (1.97%), Hexadecanamide (1.22%). The chromatogram of AQ extract revealed 11 prominent peaks, with major compounds such as Nonadecane (10.07%), Eicosane, 2-methyl- (8.86%), Eicosane (6.23%), Nonadecane, 2-methyl- (3.39%), Pentadecane (3.17%), 2-propyldecan-1-ol (2.56%), Dodecane (2.52%), 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester (1.58%). Few minor compounds such as Sulfurous acid, dodecyl 2-propyl ester (1.39%), Dodecane, 2-methyl- (1.30%) and Sulfurous acid, 2-propyl tridecyl ester (1.16%) were also detected [33]. The structural identification of compounds from GC retention data is based on spectral comparison and matching with NIST library (National Institute of Standards and Technology). The minor peaks may correspond to the compounds present in low concentrations or breakdown products of major compounds [15]. The GC-MS profile of a freshwater gastropod, *Cipangopaludina lecythis*, revealed the presence of a few similar compounds to the *M. casta* extracts, such as eicosane [34]. Another freshwater mollusc, *P. globosa*, contains most of the compounds also reported in *M. casta* extracts, indicating a significant overlap in their chemical composition [30].

Fig. 3 GC-MS Chromatogram of 3a. Ethyl acetate, 3b. Methanolic, 3c. Aqueous extracts of *M. casta*

TABLE V
GC-MS Table of *M. casta* Ethyl Acetate Extract

RT (min)	Compound	Area %
2.452	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-	2.83
2.717	Butanoic acid	8.72
3.281	Butanoic acid, 3-methyl-	8.49
3.369	Butanoic acid, 2-methyl-	2.78
11.323	cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid	1.93
11.413	Pentadecanoic acid	17.75
11.725	Eicosanoic acid	1.83
11.904	Pentadecanoic acid	2.46
12.286	9-Tetradecenal, (Z)-	5.06
12.375	Octadecanoic acid	7.14
14.217	Cholesterol	39.81
15.997	Cholest-5-en-3-ol (3. beta.)-, carbonochloridate	1.19

TABLE VI

GC-MS Table of *M. casta* Methanolic Extract

RT (min)	Compound	Area %
2.469	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-	3.83
2.744	Butanoic acid	12.65
3.306	Butanoic acid, 3-methyl-	11.42
3.392	Butanoic acid, 2-methyl-	3.86
6.639	2-Piperidinone	7.86
7.082	Benzeneacetic acid	3.83
9.513	Thymine	6.31
11.324	6-Pentadecenoic acid, 13-methyl-, (6Z)-	1.97
11.414	n-Hexadecanoic acid	22.16
11.902	Pentadecanoic acid	2.73
12.286	cis-9-Hexadecenal	5.87
12.374	Pentadecanoic acid	8.87
12.483	Hexadecanamide	1.22
14.231	Decane, 1,1-diethoxy-	2.08

TABLE VII

GC-MS Table of *M. casta* Aqueous Extract

RT (min)	Compound	Area %
13.243	2-propyldecane-1-ol	2.56
13.706	Dodecane	2.52
15.022	Pentadecane	3.17
15.716	Nonadecane	10.07
19.825	Eicosane	6.23
19.905	Sulfurous acid, 2-propyl tridecyl ester	1.16
21.784	Sulfurous acid, dodecyl 2-propyl ester	1.39
22.510	Nonadecane, 2-methyl-	3.39
23.341	Eicosane, 2-methyl-	8.86
23.878	Dodecane, 2-methyl-	1.30
23.931	1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester	1.58

B. Bacterial Identification

The isolated bacteria were identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* through Sanger sequencing using 16S rRNA-based molecular method. The obtained FASTA sequence was submitted in NCBI-Gen Bank data base and the accession number assigned was PV849231.1[35].

C. Antibacterial Activity Assay

The antibacterial potential of the three extracts of *M. casta* was assayed *in vitro* by agar well diffusion assay against *P. aeruginosa*. From the data obtained, it was evident that all the extracts show activity against *P. aeruginosa*, with MT extract showing maximum activity (Fig.4) [36]. MT extract produced exhibited zones of 16 mm at 100 µg/mL and 19 mm at 200 µg/mL, while the ethyl acetate extract exhibited zones of 15 mm and 18.67 mm and AQ extract exhibited zones of 14.67mm and 16.67mm at the same concentrations respectively [37]. The tissue extracts of *Babylonia spirata*, a marine mollusc, have been reported to show significant antimicrobial potential against several human pathogenic bacteria, with the maximum zone of inhibition observed against *P. aeruginosa* [32]. *Chicoreus ramosus*, another marine gastropod, exhibited good antibacterial activity against human pathogenic strains, as demonstrated by both its egg and tissue extracts [38]. Notable antibacterial activity was reported to be exhibited by multiple other mollusc species such as *Perna viridis* [39], *Crassostrea madrasensis* [40], *Achatina fulica férussac* [41]. These findings serve as strong evidence supporting the antibacterial potential of various molluscan extracts, highlighting the promise of *M. casta* extracts as well.

Figure 4 summarizes the bacterial growth inhibition zone of ethyl acetate, methanolic and aqueous extracts of *M. casta*. Figure 5 represent antibacterial activity of the three *M. casta* extracts.

Fig. 4 Antibacterial activity of different extracts of *M. casta*.

Fig. 5 Zones of inhibition exhibited by *P. aeruginosa* against different *M. casta* extracts

D. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The MIC of EA, MT and AQ extracts of *M. casta* was assessed against *P. aeruginosa*. The bacterial growth inhibition activity of *M. casta* extracts at 10 different concentrations from 100 µg/ml till 0.19 µg/ml is shown in figure 6-8 [42,43]. In all extracts, the MIC value is found to lie around 6.25 µg/mL as that's the minimum concentration at which >80 inhibition is observed. The IC₅₀ values for the three extracts were determined as 2.23 µg/mL, 1.59 µg/mL and 3.13 µg/mL for EA, MT and AQ extracts, respectively. This suggests that MT is the most potent extract, followed by EA and AQ extracts. These results can be compared to the methanolic extract of *Thais savignyi*, a marine gastropod, which exhibited antibacterial potential against *P. aeruginosa* with MIC values of 100 µg/mL [44]. Additionally, the methanolic extract of *Planaxis sulcatus*, a marine gastropod exhibited good antibacterial potential against *P. aeruginosa* with a MIC value of 1.87 µg/mL [45].

TABLE VIII

MIC values of *M. casta* extracts

Extracts	MIC (µg/mL)
Ethyl acetate	6.25
Methanol	6.25
Aqueous	12.5

Fig.7 Antibacterial activity of *M. casta* Methanolic extract.

Fig.8 Antibacterial activity of *M. casta* Aqueous extract.

E. Resazurin Cell Viability Assay

Resazurin serves as an oxidation–reduction indicator used to evaluate cell viability. Initially a blue, non-fluorescent dye, it turns pink and fluorescent when it is reduced to resorufin by oxidoreductases present in the viable cells [46]. The blue colour signifies non-viable cells (inhibition) and pink colour indicates active metabolism and viable cells. The Resazurin assay plates when observed after 20 minutes of incubation exhibited significant colour change which was carefully observed and interpreted as indicator of cell viability. The results suggested that EA and ME extracts have strong antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* as they had retained blue colour till their MIC, i.e. 6.25 µg/mL, while the AQ extract was the least effective when compared with the blue colour retaining only till 12.5 µg/mL (Fig.9). These results are in agreement with the MIC assay results. In a similar study, the resazurin assay was performed in extracts of a marine Gastropod, *Planaxis sulcatus*, to determine the MIC values against human pathogenic bacteria [47]. The effectiveness of the resazurin assay has been well documented in a study of marine invertebrate extracts, which reported this assay as a reliable and faster method [48]. As the same assay is used in the present study, it further ensures the accuracy and credibility of the MIC results obtained.

Fig.9 Resazurin cell viability assay.

F. Anti-Biofilm Assay

The *M. casta* extracts exhibited dose dependent biofilm inhibition activity against *P. aeruginosa* where an increase in the extract concentration progressively led to reduced biofilm formation. A remarkable reduction in preformed biofilms was noted. EA extract at a range of concentrations from 25 to 50 µg/mL inhibited biofilm formation by approximately 50%. The ME extract showed similar inhibition around

25µg/mL, and AQ extract achieved 50% inhibition at higher range of concentrations ranging from 50 to 100µg/mL. These findings suggest that the highest antibiofilm potential is possessed by ME extract, followed by EA and AQ extracts [49]. According to the established criteria, a biofilm inhibition percentage greater than 50% is considered as effective antibiofilm activity, whereas percentage inhibition in-between 0–49% is considered as weak or poor. In this context, significant antibiofilm activity was demonstrated by the three extracts. The positive control streptomycin showed around 59.26% biofilm inhibition, whereas the negative control (sterile distilled water and fresh LB broth) did not reveal any inhibition but helped enhance the biofilm production slightly [43,50]. Notably, the plasma fractions of a freshwater mussel, *Anodonta cygnea* exhibited significant antibiofilm activity against few bacteria including *P. aeruginosa* even at diluted concentrations [51]. Additionally, studies have shown that the hemolymph of *Pomacea canaliculate*, *Achatina fulica*, and *Lamellidens marginalis* disrupt *P. aeruginosa* biofilm formation [52]. These findings reinforce the potential of marine molluscs as promising antibiofilm agents and support the need for further studies to identify and develop bioactive compounds for therapeutic applications to prevent biofilm-associated infections. Overall, these findings indicate the significant antibacterial and antibiofilm properties of the *M. Casta* extracts, especially the ME and EA extracts. The antibiofilm potential of the *M. casta* extracts is shown in Figure 10.

Fig.10 Antibiofilm activity of *M. casta* extracts

V. CONCLUSION

This study emphasizes the significant bioactive potential of ethyl acetate, methanolic and aqueous extracts of *Meretrix casta*, demonstrating significant antibacterial and antibiofilm properties. The dose-dependent inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* reported in this study aligns with findings reported in other marine organisms, indicating a strong antibacterial property within the marine ecosystem. The bioactive compounds discovered by zoochemical characterization reinforces on the pharmacological value of *M. casta* extracts as source of potential drugs. These findings highlight the relevance of marine biodiversity, especially marine molluscs as valuable source of natural bioactive compounds. Future studies should focus on isolating these bioactive compounds, elucidating their mechanisms of action and assessing their effectiveness for potential therapeutic applications. Molluscs are abundantly available in the marine habitats yet they remain unexplored and underutilized compared to other marine organisms. Hence, this study was conducted to

ascertain both the antibacterial properties and the characterization of marine clam *Meretrix casta* extracts, to explore their use for therapeutic uses.

VI. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Marine invertebrates remain as an unexplored source of potential novel bioactive compounds of huge medicinal value. Future research can focus on isolation, purification and characterization of these compounds in a large scale, along with deep studies on their scope in clinical applications. Use of advanced biotechnology tools like proteomics, genomics and metabolomics, along with use of improved extraction and solvent optimization protocols could help in improving the yield and accuracy. Broader applications of this work hold great significance, including development of new drugs for diabetes, antibiotic resistance, anti-biofilm activity and oxidative stress-related disorders. Further research is essential to develop these marine obtained drugs into clinically safe and effective drugs.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Datta D, Talapatra N, Swarnakar S. Bioactive compounds from marine invertebrates for potential medicines – An overview. *International Letters of Natural Sciences* 2015.
- [2] P Walag AM. Bioactivities of Extracts from Different Marine Organisms around the World (2000 to Present). *BJSTR* 2017;1. <https://doi.org/10.26717/BJSTR.2017.01.000600>.
- [3] Jaspars M, De Pascale D, Andersen JH, Reyes F, Crawford AD, Ianora A. The marine biodiscovery pipeline and ocean medicines of tomorrow. *J Mar Biol Ass* 2016;96:151–8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315415002106>.
- [4] De Zoysa M. Medicinal Benefits of Marine Invertebrates. *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research*, vol. 65, Elsevier; 2012, p. 153–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-416003-3.00009-3>.
- [5] Thippesh D, Velayudhannair K. Analysis of zoochemical from *Meretrix casta* (Mollusca: Bivalvia) extracts, collected from Rameswaram, Tamil Nadu, India and their pharmaceutical activities. *Journal of Integrated Science and Technology* 2024;12:835–835.
- [6] Nakajima R, Shigeno S, Zullo L, De Sio F, Schmidt MR. Cephalopods Between Science, Art, and Engineering: A Contemporary Synthesis. *Front Commun* 2018;3:20. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2018.00020>.
- [7] Khan BM, Liu Y. Marine Mollusks: Food with Benefits. *Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safe* 2019;18:548–64. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12429>.
- [8] Liu M, Wei J, Wang H, Ding L, Zhang Y, Lin X. Extract of *Meretrix meretrix* Linnaeus induces angiogenesis in vitro and activates endothelial nitric oxide synthase. *Chin J Ocean Limnol* 2012;30:724–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00343-012-1241-5>.
- [9] Paduhilao II JE, Yap-Dejeto LG. Zoochemical Analyses and In vitro Antimicrobial Activity of Crude Methanolic Extract of *Perna viridis*. *Acta Medica Philippina* 2022;56.
- [10] Walag AMP, Del Rosario RM, Canencia OP. Zoochemical composition of selected sea stars collected from the Coastal Waters of Carmen, Agusan Del Norte, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Biological and Life Sciences* 2019;8:53.
- [11] Thamizharasan R, Ravichandran R. Zoo-Chemical Profile Analysis of Ten Marine Mollusca Shells Using Different Solvents From Vedaranyam, South-East Coast of Tamilnadu, India. *UTTAR PRADESH JOURNAL OF ZOOLOGY* 2023;44:46–52.
- [12] Thawabteh AM, Swaileh Z, Ammar M, Jaghama W, Yousef M, Karaman R, A. Bufo S, Scrano L. Antifungal and antibacterial activities of isolated marine compounds. *Toxins* 2023;15:93.
- [13] Defer D, Bourgougnon N, Fleury Y. Screening for antibacterial and antiviral activities in three bivalve and two gastropod marine molluscs. *Aquaculture* 2009;293:1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.03.047>.
- [14] Alara OR, Abdurahman NH, Ukaegbu CI, Kabbashi NA. Extraction and characterization of bioactive compounds in *Vernonia amygdalina* leaf ethanolic extract comparing Soxhlet and microwave-assisted extraction techniques. *Journal of Taibah University for Science* 2019;13:414–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16583655.2019.1582460>.

- [15] Jain PK, Soni A, Jain P, Bhawsar J. Phytochemical analysis of *Mentha spicata* plant extract using UV-VIS, FTIR and GC/MS technique 2016.
- [16] Patle TK, Shrivastava K, Kurrey R, Upadhyay S, Jangde R, Chauhan R. Phytochemical screening and determination of phenolics and flavonoids in *Dillenia pentagyna* using UV-vis and FTIR spectroscopy. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 2020;242:118717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2020.118717>.
- [17] Kainat S, Gilani SR, Asad F, Khalid MZ, Khalid W, Ranjha MMAN, Bangar SP, Lorenzo JM. Determination and Comparison of Phytochemicals, Phenolics, and Flavonoids in *Solanum lycopersicum* Using FTIR Spectroscopy. *Food Anal Methods* 2022;15:2931–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12161-022-02344-w>.
- [18] Speirs JP, Anderton A, Anderson JG. A study of the microbial content of the domestic kitchen. *International Journal of Environmental Health Research* 1995;5:109–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603129509356839>.
- [19] Drancourt M, Berger P, Raoult D. Systematic 16S rRNA Gene Sequencing of Atypical Clinical Isolates Identified 27 New Bacterial Species Associated with Humans. *J Clin Microbiol* 2004;42:2197–202. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.42.5.2197-2202.2004>.
- [20] Oyetayo VO, Dong C-H, Yao Y-J. Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Properties of Aqueous Extract from *Dictyophora indusiata*. *TOMYCI* 2009;3:20–6. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874437000903010020>.
- [21] Eloff J. A Sensitive and Quick Microplate Method to Determine the Minimal Inhibitory Concentration of Plant Extracts for Bacteria. *Planta Med* 1998;64:711–3. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2006-957563>.
- [22] Nkala BA, Mbongwa HP, Qwebani-Ogunleye T. The in vitro evaluation of some South African plant extracts for minimum inhibition concentration and minimum bactericidal concentration against selected bacterial strains. *IJSRP* 2019;9:p91132. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.9.07.2019.p91132>.
- [23] Casey JT, O’Cleirigh C, Walsh PK, O’Shea DG. Development of a robust microtiter plate-based assay method for assessment of bioactivity. *Journal of Microbiological Methods* 2004;58:327–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2004.04.017>.
- [24] Teh CH, Nazni WA, Nurulhusna AH, Norazah A, Lee HL. Determination of antibacterial activity and minimum inhibitory concentration of larval extract of fly via resazurin-based turbidometric assay. *BMC Microbiol* 2017;17:36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-017-0936-3>.
- [25] Hussain AI, Anwar F, Nigam PS, Sarker SD, Moore JE, Rao JR, Mazumdar A. Antibacterial activity of some Lamiaceae essential oils using resazurin as an indicator of cell growth. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* 2011;44:1199–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2010.10.005>.
- [26] Qasim N, Shahid M, Yousaf F, Riaz M, Anjum F, Faryad MA, Shabbir R. Therapeutic Potential of Selected Varieties of *Phoenix Dactylifera* L. Against Microbial Biofilm and Free Radical Damage to DNA. Dose-Response 2020;18:1559325820962609. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559325820962609>.
- [27] Famuyide IM, Aro AO, Fasina FO, Eloff JN, McGaw LJ. Antibacterial and antibiofilm activity of acetone leaf extracts of nine under-investigated south African *Eugenia* and *Syzygium* (Myrtaceae) species and their selectivity indices. *BMC Complement Altern Med* 2019;19:141. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-019-2547-z>.
- [28] Djordjevic D, Wiedmann M, McLandsborough LA. Microtiter Plate Assay for Assessment of *Listeria monocytogenes* Biofilm Formation. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 2002;68:2950–8. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.68.6.2950-2958.2002>.
- [29] Williams ST, Ito S, Wakamatsu K, Goral T, Edwards NP, Wogelius RA, Henkel T, De Oliveira LFC, Maia LF, Strekopytov S, Jeffries T, Speiser DI, Marsden JT. Identification of Shell Colour Pigments in Marine Snails *Clanculus pharaonius* and *C. margaritarius* (Trochoidea; Gastropoda). *PLoS ONE* 2016;11:e0156664. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0156664>.
- [30] Pandirajan S., Samuel S., Iswaran V., Venkatachalam RS. GC- MS SCREENING AND IN-SILICO PREDICTION OF PILA GLOBOSA EXTRACT AGAINST THE BONE DISEASES IN CALCITONIN RECEPTOR. *JASR* 2022;13:69–84. <https://doi.org/10.55218/jasr.2022131111>.
- [31] Krishnan S, Chakraborty K. Functional Properties of Ethyl Acetate-methanol Extract of Commonly Edible Molluscs. *Journal of Aquatic Food Product Technology* 2019;28:729–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10498850.2019.1638857>.
- [32] Periyasamy N, Srinivasan M, Balakrishnan S. Antimicrobial activities of the tissue extracts of *Babylonia spirata* Linnaeus, 1758 (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from Thazhanguda, southeast coast of India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine* 2012;2:36–40. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2221-1691\(11\)60186-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2221-1691(11)60186-x).
- [33] Pandian RS, Noora AT. GC-MS Analysis of Phytochemical Compounds Present in the Leaves of *Citrus medica*. *L. Rese Jour of Pharm and Technol* 2019;12:1823. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-360X.2019.00304.4>.
- [34] Ngangbam AK, Nongmaithem BD, Dai VT, Lenin L, Khundrakpam L, Pinky L, Irom P, Sharma HSS. Advancing the discovery of bioactive compounds, its extraction and identification from the underexplored mollusc, *Cipangopaludina lecythis* (W. H. Benson, 1836). *Fish Aquat Sci* 2024;27:539–51. <https://doi.org/10.47853/fas.2024.e51>.
- [35] Naji HF, Saleh MA. GENETIC DIVERSITY AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE PATTERNS OF *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA* ISOLATES FROM IRAQI HOSPITALS 2024;5.

- [36] Parekh J, Chanda S. In vitro Antimicrobial Activity and Phytochemical Analysis of Some Indian Medicinal Plants n.d.
- [37] Thippesh D, Velayudhannair K. Exploring the Pharmaceutical Potential of *Meretrix casta* (Gmelin, 1791) (Mollusca: Bivalvia). *Ajc* 2025;37:1469–76. <https://doi.org/10.14233/ajchem.2025.33827>.
- [38] Screening of antibacterial drugs from marine gastropod *Chicoreus ramosus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *JCLM* 2013. <https://doi.org/10.12980/jclm.1.20132013j5>.
- [39] Chandran B, Rameshkumar G, Ravichandran S. Antimicrobial Activity from the Gill Extraction of *Perna viridis* (Linnaeus, 1758) 2009.
- [40] . NA, . RA, . SJ, . RT. Antibacterial Activities of Green Mussel (*Perna viridis*) and Edible Oyster (*Crassostrea madrasensis*). *Research J of Microbiology* 2007;2:978–82. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jm.2007.978.982>.
- [41] Kubota Y, Watanabe Y, Otsuka H, Tamiya T, Tsuchiya T, Matsumoto JJ. Purification and characterization of an antibacterial factor from snail mucus. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Comparative Pharmacology* 1985;82:345–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-8413\(85\)90173-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-8413(85)90173-2).
- [42] Goh SM, Dassanayake MK, Foan CC, Wiart C, Symonds R, Khoo T-J, Chong CH, Elfar OA. Antibacterial potency of mid-polar extracts obtained from Malaysian plant *Parkia speciosa* against human pathogenic bacteria. *Microbial Pathogenesis* 2025;198:107134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2024.107134>.
- [43] Rather MA, Gupta K, Gupta AK, Mishra P, Qureshi A, Dutta TK, Joardar SN, Mandal M. Phytochemical Analysis and Demonstration of Antioxidant, Antibacterial, and Antibiofilm Activities of Ethnomedicinal Plants of North East India. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol* 2023;195:3257–94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12010-022-04273-0>.
- [44] Ameri A, Shushizadeh MR, Bagher Nabavi SM, Espere F, Zarei Ahmady A. Antibacterial Evaluation and Biochemical Characterization of *Thais savignyi* Gastropod Extracts from the Persian Gulf. *Jundishapur J Nat Pharm Prod* 2017;12. <https://doi.org/10.5812/jjnpp.13942>.
- [45] M SK, Haragi SB. Screening of Novel Bioactive Natural Compounds and their Antibacterial Property from Resilient Marine Gastropod *Planaxis sulcatus* (Born, 1778) Collected from Karwar coast, West coast of India. *J Adv Zool* 2023;44:174–90. <https://doi.org/10.17762/jaz.v44i2.362>.
- [46] Sarker SD, Nahar L, Kumarasamy Y. Microtitre plate-based antibacterial assay incorporating resazurin as an indicator of cell growth, and its application in the in vitro antibacterial screening of phytochemicals. *Methods* 2007;42:321–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2007.01.006>.
- [47] J.Jenifer, Renuga FB. Marine Gastropod *Planaxis sulcatus* (Born, 1778) of Uvari Coastal Waters: A Comprehensive Study on Its Antibacterial Activity, Biochemical Composition and FTIR Spectroscopy. *UPJOZ* 2024;45:417–24. <https://doi.org/10.56557/upjoz/2024/v45i204597>.
- [48] Fajarningsih ND, Munifah I, Zilda DS. Evaluation of Antibacterial Assays for Screening of Marine Invertebrate Extracts. *Squalen Bull Marine Fisheries Postharvest Biotech* 2018;13:1. <https://doi.org/10.15578/squalen.v13i1.294>.
- [49] De Moura DF, Rocha TA, De Melo Barros D, Da Silva MM, Dos Santos Santana M, Neta BM, Cavalcanti IMF, Martins RD, Da Silva MV. Evaluation of the antioxidant, antibacterial, and antibiofilm activity of the sesquiterpene nerolidol. *Arch Microbiol* 2021;203:4303–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00203-021-02377-5>.
- [50] Adeosun IJ, Baloyi IT, Cosa S. Anti-Biofilm and Associated Anti-Virulence Activities of Selected Phytochemical Compounds against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Plants* 2022;11:1429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11111429>.
- [51] Hinzmann M, Bessa LJ, Teixeira A, Costa PMD, Machado J. Antimicrobial and Antibiofilm Activity of Unionid Mussels from the North of Portugal. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 2018;37:121–9. <https://doi.org/10.2983/035.037.0110>.
- [52] Soren M, Mishra SK, Mishra AK, Rauta PR, Panda J, Rustagi S, Rahman S, Mohanta YK, Nayak D. Assessment of toxicity profile of Mollusca hemolymph: Insight into its potential biocompatibility and anti-biofilm efficacy. *Kuwait Journal of Science* 2025;52:100455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjs.2025.100455>.